

PERSONAL HYGIENE AWARENESS AND PRACTICES IN TEMPORARY ACCOMMODATION FACILITIES

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to evaluate short-term changes in hygiene knowledge and awareness following a practical hygiene training program implemented in a container city after the February 6, 2023, earthquakes. A single-group pre-test-post-test quasi-experimental design was used. The study was conducted with 32 parent participants living in a container city in Hatay province, each representing a household. Although the training program included practical activities for both adults and children, the quantitative evaluation was based only on pre-test and post-test data collected from parents. Participants received a three-week hands-on training program covering personal hygiene, proper handwashing, food and water safety, and oral health. Data were collected using a 20-item Hygiene Knowledge and Awareness Test developed by the researchers. The mean age of participants was 42.15 years, and 75% were female. The mean total score increased from 73.59 before the training to 89.53 after the training. This difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). Analyses by thematic item groups showed significant increases in personal/hand hygiene and food and water safety scores, whereas the increase in oral and dental health scores was not statistically significant. The findings suggest that the practical hygiene training program was associated with a short-term increase in hygiene knowledge and awareness among parent participants in the studied container city. However, the results should be interpreted cautiously due to the single-group quasi-experimental design, small sample size, and absence of direct behavioral observation. Hygiene training in post-disaster temporary shelters should be planned together with adequate water, sanitation, and physical infrastructure conditions.

INTRODUCTION

Naturally induced disasters, particularly destructive earthquakes, necessitate mass sheltering in temporary housing areas (tent and container cities). In disaster management, one of the greatest risks posed by communal living in temporary housing areas established following the emergency response phase is the spread of infectious diseases (Watson et al., 2007). In this context, protecting public health in the post-disaster period depends not only on infrastructure improvements but also on supporting the health and hygiene practices of individuals in these shelter areas.

“Hygiene refers to conditions and practices that help to maintain health and prevent the spread of diseases.” (WHO, 2026). In daily life, hygiene encompasses behaviors such as handwashing, personal hygiene, the use of clean water, and sanitation practices, and directly affects an individual’s health (Sphere Association, 2018).

The February 6, 2023, earthquakes, in addition to the physical destruction they caused, also created urgent needs for water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) infrastructure in the temporary shelters of disaster victims (TMMOB, 2023). In temporary shelter conditions, respiratory infections, diseases transmitted via the fecal-oral route, and diarrhea are among the most common public health threats (Bostan, 2024). The most fundamental way to minimize these risks is to establish proper handwashing habits with water and soap, ensure safe food storage and consumption under limited resources, and make general personal hygiene and oral health (toothbrushing) practices sustainable. Current studies in the literature indicate that even when physical hygiene materials (hygiene kits, soap, toothbrushes, etc.) are provided in post-crisis living areas, the desired lasting behavioral change cannot be achieved if this supply process is not supported by practical training (Biran et al., 2012). Particularly in container living, where food preparation facilities are more limited compared to standard housing, food and hand hygiene emerge as a structural factor that directly affects not only the individual but the entire camp population.

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The Sphere Project (Humanitarian Charter and Minimum Standards in Humanitarian Action), which establishes a fundamental standard for global humanitarian aid interventions, addresses post-disaster survival and health protection strategies in an integrated manner through the Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH) components (Sphere Association, 2018). According to Sphere standards, the success of WASH interventions depends not only on the physical provision of clean water and sanitation facilities but also on “hygiene promotion and capacity-building” efforts that ensure the community uses these resources properly. In environments with high population density, such as container cities, where shared living spaces are limited and physical infrastructure is sometimes inadequate, raising individuals’ awareness of protecting their own health is of critical importance (Behnke et al., 2024).

In this context, fostering hygiene habits among individuals living in container cities established after an earthquake should be an integral part of post-disaster recovery policies. This study was conducted to examine the impact of practical hygiene training program provided to individuals living in post-disaster container cities on participants’ short-term levels of hygiene knowledge and awareness, in line with the international WASH approach and the Sphere Minimum Standards. While the program included practical activities for both adults and children, the quantitative evaluation of the study was based on the pre-test and post-test scores of the parents participating in the research, representing each household. In this regard, the study aims to provide field-based preliminary findings regarding small-scale, feasible, and measurable public health education interventions that can be implemented in long-term temporary housing areas following a disaster.

While the existing literature highlights the importance of post-disaster WASH interventions, there are limited field-based studies in Türkiye that evaluate practical hygiene training programs conducted in long-term temporary shelters following an earthquake using pre-test and post-test data. Furthermore, short-term knowledge gains and lasting behavioral change are not the same concepts; therefore, clearly reporting the characteristics of the research design and measurement tools is crucial when interpreting intervention effects (Shadish et al., 2002). This study aims to address this gap by providing quantitative field data within the context of container cities. However, when evaluating educational interventions conducted

in post-disaster temporary shelters, the limitations of the research design must be clearly taken into account. While single-group pretest-posttest designs are particularly useful in preliminary assessment studies due to their feasibility in field conditions, the absence of a control group prevents the observed changes from being attributed entirely to the intervention. In such designs, factors such as test-retest effects, short-term learning, social desirability, and external conditions may influence the results (Shadish et al., 2002). Therefore, the present study is positioned not as an experimental study demonstrating the definitive causal effect of applied hygiene education, but as a field-based preliminary study evaluating short-term changes in knowledge and awareness in the context of container cities.

The main contribution of this study is that it evaluates a small-scale, practical hygiene training program conducted in post-disaster temporary shelters using pre-test and post-test data. Despite the limited sample size and field conditions, the study demonstrates that hygiene training in container cities can be measured and monitored. In this regard, the research highlights the need to plan post-disaster public health interventions not only through service delivery and material provision but also by incorporating components of education, awareness, and monitoring and evaluation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Purpose and Design of the Study

This study was conducted to evaluate short-term changes in hygiene knowledge and awareness following practical hygiene training program provided to individuals living in temporary shelters after the February 6, 2023, earthquakes. A single-group pre-test-post-test quasi-experimental design, one of the quantitative research methods, was used in the study. In this design, measurements are taken from the same participant group before and after the training to examine the changes resulting from the intervention.

While the single-group pre-test-post-test design offers a practical and feasible approach for post-disaster field conditions, it has limitations in terms of internal validity due to the absence of a control group. Therefore, the findings of this study were interpreted not as direct causal evidence, but as a preliminary assessment of the short-term changes observed following the practical hygiene training (Shadish et al., 2002). In this study, supported under the TÜBİTAK (The Scientific

and Technological Research Council of Türkiye) 2209-A “University Student Research Projects Support Program,” the independent variable is practical hygiene training program, and the dependent variable is the hygiene knowledge and awareness score.

Context and Population-Sample of the Study

The study was conducted in a container city established in Hatay Province, featuring standardized infrastructure (including individual toilet/bathroom units and a limited kitchen area).

The population of the study consists of earthquake survivors living in the relevant container city. The sample was selected using the non-probability-based “purposive sampling” method. The inclusion criteria for the study were defined as: continuing to live in the relevant container city, committing to participate in all practical training sessions, and voluntarily signing the informed consent form. The study was completed with 32 parents who met these criteria and participated in the training on behalf of each household. The fact that the sample was selected using purposive sampling and that the study was limited to a single container city restricts the generalizability of the findings. Therefore, the study presents context-specific preliminary findings rather than definitive results representing the broader population.

Participant selection was based on voluntarism, and the goal was for one parent from each household to participate in the study. The training program included hands-on activities for children; however, no quantitative data was collected from the children, and the study’s pre-test and post-test evaluations were conducted based on the responses of the parent participants. The pre-test and post-test measurements were administered to the same group of participants. Due to the study’s field conditions, the challenges of conducting research in post-disaster living areas, and the fact that participants were selected on a voluntary basis, the sample could not be selected using probability-based methods. Therefore, the findings should be interpreted as preliminary findings specific to the context of the relevant container city.

Data Collection Tools

The research data were collected using a face-to-face survey method, and the data collection tool consists of two sections:

i. Demographic Information Form: This consists of

questions prepared by the researchers to determine participants’ sociodemographic characteristics, such as gender, age, occupation, and number of children.

ii. Hygiene Knowledge and Awareness Test: Developed by researchers to assess participants’ level of knowledge regarding hygiene and their self-reported awareness indicators. The test items were developed in accordance with the principles of hygiene promotion, safe water use, hand hygiene, food hygiene, and personal hygiene emphasized in the international WASH approach and the Sphere Minimum Standards (Sphere Association, 2018). The test consists of a total of 20 items, with each correct answer scored as 5 points. Accordingly, the total score that can be obtained from the test ranges from 0 to 100; higher scores indicate a higher level of hygiene knowledge and awareness. To support the content validity of the measurement tool, the opinions of two experts in the fields of public health and disaster management were sought; the items were reviewed in terms of clarity, appropriateness, and their level of representation of the subject area. However, due to the limited number of experts, the lack of a pilot study, and the absence of detailed psychometric analyses, the test should not be considered a standardized scale. Therefore, the scores obtained in this study were interpreted not as measures indicating definitive behavioral change, but as research-specific knowledge and awareness assessment scores (Lynn, 1986; Polit & Beck, 2006).

Implementation and Training Process

Prior to the intervention, the demographic structure of the site was analyzed in coordination with the container city administration. A “pre-test” was administered to determine the participants’ initial knowledge and awareness levels. Subsequently, hands-on training sessions were conducted in small groups of 10 participants, twice a week, as part of a 3-week program:

- i. Week 1: Interactive personal hygiene information sessions were held for both participants and children.
- ii. Week 2: While environmental factors affecting general hygiene were explained to adults, child participants were given a “hands-on handwashing” simulation using gouache paint and gloves to visualize transmission routes.
- iii. Week 3: Adult participants were educated on food hygiene in confined spaces and diseases that can be transmitted

through contaminated water and food (e.g., Hepatitis A). Children were shown practical oral and toothbrushing techniques using a dental model.

Following the completion of the training program, a “final test” was administered to participants, and the resulting data was recorded. All training sessions were conducted in accordance with the standard content previously determined by the research team. The sessions utilized a combination of verbal explanations, visual materials, hands-on demonstrations, and participant-interactive methods. In activities for children, a hand-washing simulation using gouache paint and gloves was conducted to visualize transmission routes; in oral and dental health education, the correct brushing technique was demonstrated using a dental model. For adult participants, practical recommendations were provided on hand hygiene, safe water use, food storage, and personal hygiene, taking into account the limited physical conditions of container living. This approach ensured that the training was based not only on knowledge transfer but also on practical applications adaptable to daily living conditions.

Data Analysis

Statistical analysis of the data was performed using the JASP 0.96 software. Descriptive statistics were presented as frequency (n), percentage (%), mean (\bar{X}), and standard deviation (SD). The distribution of pre-test and post-test total scores was evaluated using the Shapiro-Wilk test and skewness and kurtosis coefficients. The paired t-test was used to compare pre-test and post-test scores. In interpreting the findings, not only p-values but also the mean difference, confidence interval, and effect size were taken into account. Reporting the effect size contributes to evaluating the practical importance of the findings in addition to statistical significance (Lakens, 2013).

A paired t-test was also used to compare pre-test and post-test scores for thematic item groups. An independent samples t-test and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) were applied to examine whether post-test scores differed according to demographic variables. However, due to the limited sample size and the low number of participants in some subgroups, demographic comparisons were considered exploratory analyses. A significance level of $p < 0.05$ was accepted for all statistical analyses.

Ethics

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Non-Interventional Research Ethics Committee of Hatay Mustafa Kemal University on 21.05.2025 under decision number 41.

The research was conducted in accordance with the principles of the Helsinki Declaration; participants were informed about the purpose of the study, the principles of voluntariness, the confidentiality of personal data, and their right to withdraw from the study at any time. Written informed consent was obtained from all participating parents.

RESULTS

This section presents findings regarding the sociodemographic characteristics of participants living in the container city, changes in their hygiene knowledge and awareness scores before and after the practical hygiene training, and an evaluation of these changes in relation to selected thematic item groups and sociodemographic variables.

Sociodemographic Characteristics of Participants

The mean age of the parents participating in the study (n=32) was 42.15 (SD = 10.56); 75% (n=24) were women and 25% (n=8) were men. When examining the participants’ occupational distribution, 56.3% were homemakers, 21.9% were civil servants, and the remaining group consisted of academics, security guards, and firefighters. Regarding household structure, it was found that 75.1% of the participants had more than one child (primarily 2 or 3 children) (Table 1).

Table 1. Distribution of Participants by Demographic Characteristics (n=32)

Variables	Groups	n	%
Gender	Female	24	75.0
	Male	8	25.0
Occupation	Homemaker	18	56.3
	Civil Servant	7	21.9
	Other (Academic, Security Personnel, etc.)	7	21.9
Number of Children	No Children	4	12.5
	1 Child	3	9.4
	2 Children	14	43.8
	3 or More Children	11	34.4

Source: Authors’ own work.

The Overall Effect of Hygiene Education on Knowledge and Awareness Scores

The total scores that participants achieved on the “Hygiene Knowledge and Awareness Test” before and after the practical

hygiene training program were analyzed using a paired samples t-test. The results of the analysis are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Comparison of Total Scores Before (Pre-Test) and After (Post-Test)

Measurement	n	Mean	SD	t(df)	p	Cohen’s d
Pre-test	32	73.59	12.00	-7.119	<0.001	1.258
Post-test	32	89.53	7.66			

Source: Authors’ own work.

As shown in Table 2, while the mean pre-training hygiene knowledge and awareness score for participants was 73.59 (SD = 12.00), this mean increased to 89.53 (SD = 7.66) after the training. The difference between pre-test and post-test scores is statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). The Cohen’s d value of 1.258, calculated to indicate the effect size, suggests that the increase in scores observed after the training signifies a substantial change in practical terms (Cohen, 1988; Lakens, 2013). However, since the study was conducted using a single-group pre-test-post-test design, this increase should not be entirely attributed to the intervention. The findings indicate that a significant increase in short-term hygiene knowledge and awareness levels was observed following the practical hygiene training (Shadish et al., 2002).

The Effect of Practical Hygiene Training Program by Thematic Groups

To examine in which subject areas the observed increase in total scores was more pronounced, the test items were evaluated under thematic groups consistent with the training content. These thematic groups were treated not as standardized subscales, but as subject headings reflecting the training content. Pre-test and post-test scores related to Personal and Hand Hygiene, Food and Water Safety, and Oral and Dental Health were compared using a paired t-test.

The test items were evaluated across three thematic groups: Personal and Hand Hygiene (8 items, maximum 40 points), Food and Water Safety (8 items, maximum 40 points), and Oral and Dental Health (4 items, maximum 20 points). Thematic group scores were calculated by summing the points obtained from the relevant items.

Table 3. Comparison of Pre-Test and Post-Test Scores by Thematic Groups

Thematic Item Group	Measurement	n	Mean	SD	t	p
Personal and Hand Hygiene	Pre-test	32	23.75	5.96	-8.463	<0.001
	Post-test	32	34.22	4.42		
Food and Water Safety	Pre-test	32	31.56	6.89	-2.135	0.041
	Post-test	32	35.00	6.35		
Oral and Dental Health	Pre-test	32	17.81	3.09	-1.877	0.070
	Post-test	32	18.91	2.45		

Source: Authors’ own work.

The thematic group analysis showed that the most pronounced improvement occurred in Personal and Hand Hygiene scores, which increased from 23.75 to 34.22 out of 40 points. A smaller but statistically significant improvement was also observed in Food and Water Safety scores, which increased from 31.56 to 35.00. In contrast, the increase in Oral and Dental Health scores was not statistically significant. This may

be partly explained by the high baseline score in this thematic area, suggesting a possible ceiling effect. Therefore, the findings indicate that practical hygiene training was particularly effective in improving short-term knowledge and awareness related to hand hygiene and, to a lesser extent, food and water safety, while its measurable contribution to oral and dental health knowledge remained limited.

Comparison of Final Hygiene Test Scores by Demographic Variables

Various statistical analyses were conducted to determine whether the participants' learning outcomes from the practical

hygiene training program (final test scores) differed according to sociodemographic variables (Table 4).

Table 4. Comparison of Final Test Scores by Participants' Demographic Characteristics

Variables	Groups	n	Mean (\bar{X})	Standard Deviation (SD)	Test Statistic	p
Gender	Female	24	89.79	6.83	t = 0.328	0.745
	Male	8	88.75	10.26		
Occupation	Homemaker	18	91.66	5.67	F = 2.293	0.075
	Civil Servant	7	82.85	11.50		
	Other	7	90.71	3.45		
Number of Children	No Children	4	92.50	5.00	F = 1.183	0.341
	1 Child	3	86.66	2.88		
	2 Children	14	91.07	6.85		
	3 or More	11	86.36	9.50		

Source: Authors' own work.

Table 4 shows that the mean final test score for female participants was 89.79, while the mean for male participants was 88.75. The results of the Independent Samples t-test revealed no statistically significant difference in final test scores based on gender ($t=0.328$; $p=0.745 > 0.05$).

Similarly, according to the results of the ANOVA test conducted on final test scores based on participants' occupational groups and the number of children they have, no statistically significant difference was found ($p=0.075$ for occupation; $p=0.341$ for number of children).

Finally, the relationship between participants' ages ($\bar{X}=42.15$) and the hygiene knowledge and awareness scores they achieved after the training was examined using Pearson correlation analysis; no significant relationship was found between age and final test scores ($r=0.258$; $p=0.154 > 0.05$).

In the analyses of demographic variables, no statistically significant differences were found in final test scores based on gender, occupation, number of children, or age. However, due to the limited sample size and the relatively low number of participants in some subgroups, this finding should not be interpreted to mean that the training was equally effective across all sociodemographic groups. These analyses are exploratory in nature, and further studies with larger and more balanced samples are needed to more reliably assess potential differences between various groups.

DISCUSSION

Reduced access to preventive health services following disasters, disruptions in water and sanitation infrastructure, and communal living conditions can pose significant public health risks in terms of infectious diseases. For this reason, hygiene training in post-disaster temporary shelters can be viewed not merely as an activity that supports individual hygiene behaviors, but also as a preventive public health intervention that can contribute to reducing the risk of infectious diseases. The Sphere Standards also emphasize that WASH interventions should not be limited to the provision of physical infrastructure and materials but must be supported by hygiene promotion and community capacity-building activities (Sphere Association, 2018).

In this study, a significant increase in hygiene knowledge and awareness scores was observed following the practical hygiene training program provided to parents living in a container city after the February 6 earthquakes. The rise in the average pre-test score from 73.59 to 89.53 on the post-test suggests that structured and practical educational interventions may support short-term knowledge acquisition in post-disaster temporary shelters. However, since the study did not include a control group, it should not be claimed that this entire change was directly attributable to the educational intervention. This result should be interpreted as a significant short-term change observed following practical hygiene education (Shadish et al., 2002).

Significant improvements were observed in participants' knowledge levels, particularly regarding "handwashing times," "use of water and soap," and "cleaning of common areas." Similar studies in the literature also support the finding that hygiene education provided during disasters and crises increases individual awareness. For example, Biran et al. (2012), in their study conducted in refugee camps, emphasized that handwashing and personal hygiene education serve as a fundamental line of defense in preventing diseases transmitted via the fecal-oral route. In this study, demonstrating practical handwashing techniques using animations and gouache paint for children, and addressing food preservation and toothbrushing practices for adults, created an educational environment that supports the potential for knowledge to translate into behavior. However, since the current study did not include direct observational behavioral measurement, the results should be interpreted as an increase in knowledge and awareness rather than behavioral change.

When evaluated by thematic groups, it is noteworthy that the most significant increases occurred in the areas of personal/hand hygiene and food and water safety. This finding indicates that the training content aligns with the basic hygiene risks encountered on a daily basis in post-disaster container living. Topics such as handwashing times, the use of water and soap, safe food storage, and cleaning in shared living areas are of central importance for the prevention of infectious diseases in temporary shelters. Therefore, the study's findings suggest that hygiene education should be supported by practical applications adapted to daily living conditions rather than abstract informational activities.

The lack of a significant improvement in oral and dental health is one of the study's key findings. This result may be related to the relatively high pre-test scores in this area; in other words, the fact that participants already possessed a certain level of knowledge on this topic prior to the training may have limited the improvement that could be observed in the post-test. Furthermore, oral and dental health practices are related not only to knowledge levels but also to factors such as regular access to water, adequate physical space for personal care, privacy, and the sustainability of daily routines. However, since these structural variables were not directly measured in the current study, these explanations should be considered as possible interpretations consistent with the literature rather than empirical findings.

However, the most critical point of discussion in this study is the contradiction between individual knowledge gains and structural (infrastructural) deficiencies. Although our study demonstrates that participants theoretically learned hygiene rules (proper handwashing, safe food consumption, regular toothbrushing) and developed attitudes regarding these topics, the transformation of this knowledge into sustainable behavior is directly dependent on the physical conditions of the shelter area. Findings in the literature indicate that hygiene behaviors in post-disaster temporary living areas are integrated not only with individual knowledge levels but also with environmental and infrastructure conditions. Indeed, Calderón-Villarreal et al. (2022), in their study of camps in various countries, identified limited and irregular access to clean water as the greatest structural barrier to maintaining handwashing and personal hygiene habits.

A review of current field data from Türkiye also reveals similar structural barriers. Reports by the Union of Chambers of Turkish Engineers and Architects (TMMOB) (2023) and the research conducted by Tarakçı and Kavut (2025) on temporary housing units in Hatay highlight water outages in container cities, distrust in the quality of tap water, problems accessing hot water, and the risks posed by the intertwined nature of food preparation and bathing areas in cramped spaces. Although this study did not directly measure infrastructure conditions, the physical conditions of temporary shelter areas must be taken into account when interpreting the findings. The transformation of increased knowledge and awareness gained through hygiene education into sustainable behaviors is closely linked to structural conditions such as access to safe water, adequate sanitation, personal hygiene areas, and food storage facilities. Therefore, in post-disaster public health interventions, hygiene education should be viewed not as a standalone solution but as a complementary intervention that must be addressed in conjunction with WASH infrastructure and living space arrangements (Sphere Association, 2018).

Limitations

The findings of this study should be interpreted with certain methodological limitations in mind. First, the study was conducted using a single-group pre-test–post-test quasi-experimental design. Due to the absence of a control group, it is not possible to attribute the entire observed change between pre-test and post-test scores directly to the educational intervention. The test-retest effect, short-term learning, the

tendency toward social desirability, and external factors that may arise during the study process may have influenced the results (Shadish et al., 2002).

Second, the study was conducted with only 32 parents living in a single container city. The small sample size, the lack of probability-based selection, and the study's limitation to a single site restrict the generalizability of the findings. Therefore, the results should be interpreted as preliminary findings derived from the specific context of a single container city, rather than as definitive findings generalizable to all post-disaster temporary shelters.

Third, the Hygiene Knowledge and Awareness Test used in the study was developed by the researchers. Although the test items were prepared in accordance with WASH principles and Sphere standards and reviewed by experts, the measurement tool's comprehensive psychometric validity and reliability analyses are limited. This situation limits the interpretation of the obtained scores as precise behavioral measurements derived from a standardized scale (Lynn, 1986; Polit & Beck, 2006).

Fourth, the study does not include direct behavioral observation or long-term follow-up. Therefore, the increase in scores observed after the training should be interpreted as a short-term increase in knowledge and awareness rather than a lasting behavioral change. For future studies, it is recommended to use controlled or multi-center designs, work with larger samples, include direct observation data, and conduct follow-up measurements a certain period after the training. Additionally, reporting results in terms of mean difference, confidence interval, and effect size will enhance comparability with similar studies (Lakens, 2013).

CONCLUSION

This study evaluated short-term changes in hygiene knowledge and awareness following practical hygiene training program provided to parents living in a container city after the February 6, 2023, earthquakes. The findings indicate a significant increase in participants' total hygiene knowledge and awareness scores following the training. The increases observed particularly in the areas of personal/hand hygiene and food and water safety suggest that practical hygiene training adapted to daily living conditions could serve as a functional public health intervention in post-disaster temporary shelters. However, the results should be interpreted with caution due to

the study's single-group pre-test-post-test design, the absence of a control group, the small sample size, and the fact that behavior was not directly observed. Rather than establishing definitive causal conclusions, this study presents preliminary findings regarding short-term changes in knowledge and awareness following practical hygiene education in the context of container cities.

The results of the study suggest that incorporating practical hygiene training into standard public health practices in post-disaster temporary shelters could be beneficial. However, for these trainings to be effective and sustainable, they must be planned in conjunction with WASH infrastructure components such as access to safe water, sanitation facilities, personal hygiene areas, and food storage conditions. In this regard, the study can be linked to the Sustainable Development Goals, particularly Goal 3 "Good Health and Well-being" and Goal 6 "Clean Water and Sanitation."

For future research, it is recommended to work with larger and comparative samples, use controlled or multi-center quasi-experimental designs, conduct long-term follow-up measurements after training, and incorporate direct behavioral observations. Such studies will contribute to a more robust evaluation of the effectiveness of hygiene education interventions in post-disaster temporary shelters.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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